

Mapping policies and measures

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It anticipated that the audience for this guidance will be two-fold:

- People who are relatively new to process mapping
- and those who want to complete the mapping/ better understand the processes

Objective

- Collect initiatives from project participants
- Identify “good practises”
- Present results in Baranquilla

Most important

- Campaign of actions– policies

The role of universities

Where are the barriers?

Broad field	Narrow field	Detailed field
05 Natural sciences, mathematics and statistics	051 Biological and related sciences	0511 Biology
	052 Environment	0512 Biochemistry
	053 Physical sciences	0521 Environment sciences
	054 Mathematics and statistics	0522 Natural environments and wildlife
06 Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)	061 Information and communication technologies	0531 Chemistry
		0532 Earth sciences
		0533 Physics
		0541 Mathematics
		0542 Statistics
		0611 Computer use
07 Engineering, manufacturing and construction	071 Engineering and engineering trades	0612 Database and network design and administration
		0613 Software and applications development and analysis
		0711 Chemical engineering and processes
		0712 Environmental protection technology
		0713 Electricity and energy
		0714 Electronics and automation
	072 Manufacturing and processing	0715 Mechanics and metal trades
		0716 Motor vehicles, ships and aircraft
		0721 Food processing
		0722 Materials (glass, paper, plastic and wood)
073 Architecture and construction	0723 Textiles (clothes, footwear and leather)	
	0724 Mining and extraction	
		0731 Architecture and town planning
		0732 Building and civil engineering

Where are the barriers?

The role of universities

Getting more women into STEM careers will require a partnership among parents, educational institutions, government, industry, and organizations

- Among the most important actors;
- Several universities in Latin American and Europe:
 - ✓ Policies and plans in place for the institutionalisation and mainstreaming of the gender equality approach
 - ✓ activities that are addressing gender equality at different level

What should be collected and analysed

What should be collected and analysed

- Plans, strategies and policies
- Measures and initiatives
- Institutional framework

At different levels (university, department etc.)- if possible

At any stage

- planning/execution/evaluation or closing phases
- in development
- already finished

Why also mapping previous plans and activities

What works, what doesn't

This type of info would be very relevant as it would avoid replication of practices or even parts of practices that do not have a high success rate.

Plans, strategies and policies

- From those on academic and research to those on human resources, admission and governance.
- Directives and ethical principles document
- Some universities might also have specific policies addressing gender equality in STEM or to attract and retain more women in the STEM fields
- Targets (usually covers students, academics, administrative staff, personnel and people who provide services at the premises belonging to the universities)

Gender equality plan as a tool for structural change

- University of the Highlands and Islands of Scotland included specifically activities to promote women in STEM

- The College's Strategic Plan identifies the priority of investing and growing STEM provision and in particular to increasing female participation (University of Oulu)

Think questions such as:

Does the university has a plan or a policy?

- Yes
- Yes, a previous policy or plan existed but is no longer in effect
- No, but one is currently in development
- No

If yes, how it incorporates gender equality?

Which influence it has in the process of

- Attraction
- Access and enrolment
- Guidance and retention
- Advancement

It was readapted or redesigned?

Why to provide more info?

The information gap

Institutional framework

Department or a unit dedicated to gender equality (in STEM)

- Universidad de la República del Uruguay has an Open Commission on Gender Equality that began operating in 2012
- Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica- Office of Gender Equality (2013) to promote equal opportunities by improving women's access to education and work in the fields of science and technology
- In Argentina, the Universidad Nacional de San has a Directorate of Gender and Sexual Diversity
- Sexual harassment monitoring unit in some french universities

- *Gender Balance Committee* (2013 *Centre for Genomic Regulation* in Spain:) for equal opportunities. Promote equal opportunities for all individuals alongside the women's advancement in academia.

The committee aims to eliminate gender bias from CGR recruitment process to support women in career advancement.

Does the university has a specific departemnt?

- Yes
- Yes, an office, department, or unit existed but it no longer in place
- No, an office, department, or unit is currently in development
- No, it never existed

If yes, gather info such as:

- Official name of the office, department or unit
- Year of establishment
- Goals and objectives
- Function and responsibilities

Measures and initiatives

- **Relevance**, meaning that the objectives are in line with beneficiaries' gender-equality priorities and needs.
- **Efficiency**, meaning that the minimum necessary amount of resources (funds, time, expertise, etc.) have been used to produce the desired results
- **Target** (measures directly affecting students, researchers, measures orientated towards changing the institutional culture and protocols, and measures questioning the neutrality of scientific disciplines)

Which information should be collected for each initiative?

- General information:

Title of the practice, year (established and expected end), annual budget allocated

- Short description of the initiative and Main goal(s)

- Type(s) of mechanism

E.G: scholarships or fellowships, award, training etc.

- Target group

- In which stage of development is the practice

Design, execution, evaluation, ended

Which information should be collected for each initiative?

Evaluation of the practice [OPTIONAL]

- Results and outcomes of the activity
- Transferability
- Indicators and targets associated with this activity or measure in case have been developed
- It was supported by the Direction or Rectorate bodies ?

Which are the axes

Axes to address

Attraction

Attraction

What universities are doing to engage more women in studying STEM?

Target: prospective female students

Proliferation of initiatives in the latest years

Causes that have contributed to failed recruitment efforts

- including social factors
- institutional structures
- poor advising
- and early education classroom environments

Activities to attract women into STEM

- attraction campaigns and strong outreach programs within the K-12 sector, summer bridge and orientation programs
- presenting the broad applications of science and engineering to students early in their college career to build students' interest and confidence
- Open days and school career talks

Examples

- Universidad Nacional del Litoral- Bringing Down Stereotypes.
Women scientists of the past, present and future
an initiative focused on changing stereotypes towards women in STEM and attracting more women (sensitizing primary and secondary school students to gender and science).
- Faculty of Engineering of UDELAR in Uruguay
Female teachers from the Institutes of Computing and Electrical organize workshops on robotics, electrical circuits and geographic software for groups of adolescent women from secondary schools

Female-only science programs- Sex discrimination?

The U.S. Department of Education opened **two dozen investigations into universities**

UCLA, the University of Southern California and the University of California, Berkeley, as well as Yale, Princeton and Rice:

offer female-only scholarships, awards, professional development workshops and even science and engineering camps for middle and high school girls

Access and enrolment

Admissions policies

- Additional points are given to women for stimulating the insertion of women in STEM
 - MICITT and Cornell University in Costa Rica
 - University of Technology Sydney makes 10-point adjustment
 - Kenya University has been lowering the cut-off points for university entry for females by one point
- Revising admissions policies to send a more inclusive message

Action towards preventing gender bias in the student admission

- gender training for admissions counselors
- gender-balanced selection committees

University of Graz- workshop: Bias-sensitizing. Quality assurance for personnel selection. It is showing how gender bias in the personnel selection harms the selection process itself.

Quotas or other measures aiming to influence the gender balance

- Faculty of Physical and Mathematical Sciences of the University of Chile:
Programa de Ingreso Prioritario de Equidad de Género (PEG)
It offers 55 special vacancies for women on the waiting list

Campaings

- We Are HERE a communication campaign endorsed by Politecnico di Torino as a part of the project to promote enrollment in Engineering courses by women

Guidance and Retention

Guidance and Retention

Traditionally, institutions focus primarily on recruitment and little on what to do with women once they arrive on campus to ensure degree completion

<<recruiting women will be truly successful only if women who start in engineering and computing stay in these fields>> Corbett and Hill [\(2015\)](#)

In colleges and universities, little changes can make a big difference both in attracting and retaining women in STEM

Most common barriers

- Bias (un/conscious)
- Discrimination/sexism
- Harassment
- Lack of mentors
- Lack of role models
- Networking/ conference

Support work-life balance

- Stop the clock policies
- promote day care/child care facilities for students

(work/life balance policies and practices at the research centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts)

Prevent gender-based discrimination and harassment

- Workshops. Compulsory awareness-raising session for students (Paris 7 Diderot)
- Protocols. Protocol for the Prevention, Attention and Sanction of Gender Violence, Discrimination, Harassment, and Sexual Abuses (Autonomous University of Yucatan)

Changing un/conscious bias

- support services during early undergraduate years – positive campus climate (Northwestern University)

- Radboud University : Group Mentoring Programme

Establishing mentoring programmes for female students– career counselling by women academics including post-doctoral candidates, assistant professors, and associate professors.

- PoliWo – PoliTo for Women. Counselling activities to raise the average percentage of female students enrolled in first year of engineering programmes and to achieve full gender equality in some degree programmes.
- Pwani Teknowgalz in Kenya: to bridge the gender gap and create a platform where girls are able to interact, share experiences and mentor each other at the same time.
- sponsor a “women in (STEM major)” group

Maternity, extension, paternal leave

- Absence for maternity and request for extension of scholarship
- Economic benefit in the form of child care benefit for scholarship holders and undergraduate students but also teachers, administrative and service personnel (Universidad Nacional de Quilmes)
- Extension of scholarship for paternity leave

Advancement

Advancement

It is important that all individuals get equal chances to develop and advance their scientific careers

- Target:
 - Master and PhDs
 - Staff
 - Leaders

Most common barriers

- Bias (un/conscious) in the evaluation
- Discrimination/sexism and unequal recognition
- Structural processes that indirectly produce biased results in hiring and promotion
- Psychological and sexual harassment (among others)
- Lack of role models and academic support,
- Lack of mentors
- Environments not suited to persons with family responsibilities
- Networking/ conference

- Support faculty work-life balance
- Role model and mentoring
- Preventing gender bias in financial aid processes
- Promoting gender equality in international mobility of students
- Clear criteria for evaluation
- Awards and scholarships also aiming at increasing women's visibility

Examples

The *Arctic University of Norway* (University of Tromsø – UIT): the promotion project. Increase the proportion of females in top positions, by helping female associate professors and senior lecturers to apply for promotion to full professorship.

Mothers of Science supporting grant of the Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology (BIST) that is addressing the gap that exists between the number of women in the BIST Community who are research associates or senior postdoctoral researchers and the percentage of women who are group leaders.

International Women's Computer Program (2000) by the University of Applied Sciences of the Hochschule Bremen that provide a training of excellence in technological education, exclusively for women, based on the principles of education differentiated by gender

- *Imperial College London: Elsie Widdowson Fellowship Award*

The purpose is to allow female academics to concentrate fully on their research work upon returning from parental leave. The award allows the Department / Division to release the academics from any teaching or admin duties in order to concentrate fully on research.

- *Lund University : AKKA programme* - Attracting more women to academic leadership positions. Aimed at raising gender knowledge and awareness and providing methods and tools for structural change in leadership positions in order to achieve sustainable gender equality.

Other initiatives

Workshops for leaders

- University of Geneva and University of Lausanne: Gender awareness in Academia – from principles to practice, training for leadership for rectorate, deans, gender equality commissions, professors, senior researchers.

Raising awareness of gender equality within organisations

- Gender equality projects across the university

University of Helsinki (between 2002 and 2011) small-scale gender equality projects across the university. The funding increased grass-roots engagement in gender equality work, helped to identify and address the specific problems and needs of different faculties and departments and created permanent networks and good practices

- Gender sensitive language in organisation's documents

Gender balance within the organisation (in committees, research teams etc.)

- Šiauliai University (LT): T-GAP- Election for the University Council

The aim was to increase the number of female members at the top decision-making level, through interventions and change of the University election-related processes.

The exact objective was to increase females' representation in the 2014 SU's Council election, by reaching the critical mass margin of 25%.

In general, at the institutional level, it can also be observed that:

- Some institutions or high authorities do not consider gender equality to be an important practice;
- Others have measures formally oriented toward this goal but do not apply or evaluate them systematically;
- In some institutions, when an activity is carried out, it is driven by motivated employees rather than supported by the institution with key resources, such as a budget;
- However, the number of organisations that are implementing well-developed and implemented activities focused on gender equality in STEM that are integrated into the organisation's budget with a team designated to implement them and evaluate their impact is growing.

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